

DESIGN, MANUFACTURING, TESTING AND OPTIMIZATION OF BOLT LOADED VARIABLE-AXIAL COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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Fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP)

Multi-axial vs. variable-axial

Composite design 1.0
multi-axial

Composite design 2.0
variable-axial

$\alpha \neq \text{const.}$

$s \neq \text{const.}$
 $t = f(s)$

Fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP)

Variable-axial FRP by Tailored Fiber Placement (TFP)

Composite design 2.0
variable-axial

$\alpha \neq \text{const.}$

$s \neq \text{const.}$
 $t = f(s)$

Fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP)

Variable-axial FRP by Tailored Fiber Placement (TFP)

Composite design 2.0 *variable-axial*

$\alpha \neq \text{const.}$

$s \neq \text{const.}$
 $t = f(s)$

Variable-axial composites made by Tailored Fiber Placement

From basic research to industrial deployment

TRL1 TRL4 TRL7

Multi-scale modelling and optimization methods

Process chain for variable-axial composites

Development of industrial components

How to design variable-axial composite structures?

Analysis and optimization of bolted joints made by variable-axial laminates

What in-plane fiber orientation strategy shows advantageous mechanical performance?

- Calibration of progressive damage simulation for structural optimization by experimental research
- No consideration of out-of-plane reinforcements

Dimensions of specimen

$R_1 = 25 \text{ mm}$, $R_2 = 7,5 \text{ mm}$,

$L = 170 \text{ mm}$, $t \approx 5 \text{ mm}$

Bolted joints with tailored fiber orientation in literature

1997

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Tailored fibre placement to minimise stress concentrations

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 (Received 16 February 1996; accepted 8 November 1996)

Figure 5. Patterns for TFP reinforcement of test components

1999

Interpreting load paths and stress trajectories in elasticity

D.W. Kelly and M.W. Tosh
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 University of New South Wales, Sydney, Australia

Interpreting load paths

117

Received March 1999
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Figure 17. Major principal stress trajectories (σ_{11})

Figure 18. Minor principal stress trajectories (σ_{22})

Figure 19. P_x load path contours from the integration technique

2000

Composites: Part A 31 (2000) 1047-1060

composites
 Part A: applied science
 and manufacturing
 www.elsevier.com/locate/compositesa

On the design, manufacture and testing of trajectorial fibre steering for carbon fibre composite laminates*

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School of Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering, University of New South Wales, Sydney 2052, Australia
 Received 7 May 1999; revised 15 March 2000; accepted 23 March 2000

Fig. 15. Contours of dominant principal stress.

Fig. 16. Dominant or X-direction load paths for an isotropic material.

Fig. 21. Hybrid combination of anisotropic load path and tensile principal stress trajectories.

2002

Composite Structures 57 (2002) 377-383

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Strength improvement by fibre steering around a pin loaded hole*

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Fig. 9. Reduction of fibre over stacking: (a) FEA pattern; (b) modified pattern.

Fig. 10. Effect of fibre steering on strength of the carbon fibre bolted joints.

Bolted joints with tailored fiber orientation in literature

2006

Improving the Efficiency of Fiber Steered Composite Joints using Load Path Trajectories*

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(Received February 16, 2005)
 (Accepted August 23, 2005)

Figure 9. Test curves for 90mm wide baseline specimens.

Figure 10. Test curves for 90mm wide steered fiber specimens.

Figure 11. Test curves for 70mm wide steered fiber specimens.

Figure 2. Principal stress trajectories for fiber placement.

Figure 3. Reduction of fiber over stacking near the bearing surface.

Figure 12. Test curves for 60mm wide steered fiber specimens.

Figure 13. Test curves for 60mm wide steered fiber specimens.

2006

Available online at www.sciencedirect.com
 ScienceDirect
 Composite Structures 76 (2006) 260–271

COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

www.elsevier.com/locate/comstruct

Improvement of bearing strength of laminated composites*

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^c Ecole Nationale des Arts et Industries Textiles, Laboratoire GEMTEX, 9 rue de l'Éminage – BP 30329, 59100 Roubaix, France

Available online 1 August 2006

Fig. 7. Typical layout of steered fibre samples.

Fig. 15. Dominant load path trajectories (hole diameter = 30 mm).

Fig. 8. Modification of fiber steering pattern: (a) FEA σ11 trajectory and (b) σ11 shifted 5 mm away from edge.

Fig. 9. Reduction of fiber over stacking: (a) FEA pattern and (b) modified pattern.

Fig. 16. Dimension of specimens.

Table 2
Boring test results

Group	Ultimate failure mode	Peak load (kN)	Ultimate load strength (g)	Weight (mm ²)	Bearing strength (mm ²)
Baseline	Boring [12]	9.55	367.80	42.50	26.40
Steered	Net section [14]	22.16	641.24	69.75	28.83
Modified steered	Net section [14]	25.65	500.40	56.38	31.27

2016

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 Doktor der Ingenieurwissenschaften
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Die orthotrope Wärmeleitung als numerischer Integrator
 allgemeiner Richtungsfelder mit Anwendung zur optimalen
 Faserplatzierung und Kraftflussvisualisierung

genehmigte
 Dissertation
 von
 Dipl.-Ing. Herbert Mollenhauer

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 Koreferent: Prof. Dr.-Ing. Frank Henning

Hochschule
 Karlsruher Institut für Technologie

Die Visualisierung des Kraftflusses
 in Stahlbaukonstruktionen

Bolted joints with tailored fiber orientation

Steps for optimizing design process

VA patter design based on isotropic calculations

Load Path (LP) Design

Principal Stress (PS) Design

Experimental evaluation and model calibration

Optimization of VA pattern design

VA pattern design based on isotropic calculations

Principal Stress (PS) Design

Calculation of PS directions

$$\tan 2\alpha_1 = \frac{2\sigma_{12}}{\sigma_{11} - \sigma_{22}}$$

$$\alpha_2 = \alpha_1 + \frac{\pi}{2}$$

Continuous CNC path for TFP

----- Contour line

VA pattern design based on isotropic calculations

Load Path (LP) Design [1]

Calculation of Load Path directions

$$\tan \alpha_y = \frac{\sigma_{12}}{\sigma_{11}}$$

Continuous CNC path for TFP

----- Contour line

Experimental evaluation and model calibration

Manufacturing of specimen

Experimental evaluation and model calibration

Manufacturing of specimen

Roving material: CF-HT, 400 tex (6k)

Base material: CF-HT woven fabric,
 $m_A = 380 \text{ g/m}^2$

Thickness adapted RTM molds

Epoxy resin: L20 + EPH 161

Experimental evaluation and model calibration

Specimen specification and experimental setup [2]

QI
 $m = 74 \text{ g}$
 (base line)

$[0/90/\pm 45]_{4S}$
 (base material only)

LP
 $m = 59 \text{ g}$

$[LP/\pm 45]_{4S}$

PS
 $m = 57 \text{ g}$

$[PS2/PS1/\pm 45]_{4S}$

Test setup

- Instron 8088 with hydraulic clamping
- 250 kN load cell
- Preload: 50 N
- Test speed 1 mm/min
- Number of specimens: 6

Variable-axial specimens are about 22 % lighter than QI type

Experimental evaluation and model calibration

Results: Tensile test force-displacement diagram

Experimental evaluation and model calibration

Results: Tensile test force-displacement diagram

Experimental evaluation and model calibration

Results: Quasi-plastic deformation energy

Mass-specific values

Experimental evaluation and model calibration

Results: Quasi-plastic deformation energy

Mass-specific values

Model calibration

FE-modelling and material parameters

Numerical material parameters ($\varphi = 55\%$)	
Fiber, Matrix	Composite
$E_{\parallel,f} = 238,000 \text{ MPa}$	$\sigma_{\parallel,t} = 1,409 \text{ MPa}$
$E_{\perp,f} = 16,000 \text{ MPa}$	$\sigma_{\parallel,c} = -7,40 \text{ MPa}$
$G_{\perp,f} = 50,000 \text{ MPa}$	$\sigma_{\perp,t} = 80 \text{ MPa}$
$\nu_{\perp,\parallel,f} = 0.27$	$\sigma_{\perp,c} = -140 \text{ MPa}$
$E_M = 3,150 \text{ MPa}$	$\tau_{\perp\parallel} = \tau_{\perp\perp} = 69 \text{ MPa}$
$G_M = 1,150 \text{ MPa}$	
$\nu_M = 0.37$	

Model calibration

Progressive damage simulation with parameter identification by FEMU

HASHIN Failure Criterion [3]

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \text{Fiber} \\
 \text{Matrix}
 \end{array}
 \left\{ \begin{array}{l}
 X_{FT} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{F_{1T}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2}{F_6} \right) \quad \sigma_{11} \geq 0 \\
 X_{FC} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{F_{1C}} \right)^2 \quad \sigma_{11} < 0 \\
 \\
 X_{MT} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{F_{2T}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{23}}{F_4} \right)^2 + \frac{\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2}{F_6^2} \quad \sigma_{22} \geq 0 \\
 X_{MC} = \frac{\sigma_{22}}{F_{2C}} \left[\left(\frac{F_{2C}}{2F_4} \right)^2 - 1 \right] + \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{2F_4} \right)^2 \\
 \quad + \left(\frac{\sigma_{23}}{F_4} \right)^2 + \frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{F_6^2} \quad \sigma_{22} < 0
 \end{array} \right.$$

Progressive damage modelling [3]

$$\mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix}
 \frac{C_{11}}{(1-d_f)} & C_{12} & C_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
 C_{21} & \frac{C_{22}}{(1-d_m)} & C_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
 C_{31} & C_{32} & \frac{C_{33}}{(1-d_m)} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{C_{44}}{(1-d_s)} & 0 & 0 \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{C_{55}}{(1-d_s)} & 0 \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{C_{66}}{(1-d_s)}
 \end{bmatrix}^{-1}$$

$$d_f = \begin{cases} d_{ft} & \sigma_{11} \geq 0 \\ d_{fc} & \sigma_{11} < 0 \end{cases} \quad d_m = \begin{cases} d_{mt} & \sigma_{22} \geq 0 \\ d_{mc} & \sigma_{22} < 0 \end{cases}$$

$$d_s = 1 - (1 - d_{ft}) (1 - d_{fc}) (1 - d_{mt}) (1 - d_{mc})$$

Model calibration

Progressive damage simulation with parameter identification by FEMU

Stiffness degradation parameters [4] $\rho = \{d_{ft} \quad d_{fc} \quad d_{mt} \quad d_{mc}\}$

$$\min_{\rho \in [0,1]} L_2(\rho) = \min_{\rho \in [0,1]} \frac{1}{n_{ptos}} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^{n_{ptos}} \left(\frac{y_i^E - y_i^N(\rho)}{y_i^E} \right)^2}$$

Genetic Algorithm-based [4]

PS Design – Comparison exp. vs. num. results

Conclusion and Outlook

Bolt joint loaded composites with a variable-axial fiber design shows improved quasi-plastic behavior compared to QI multi-axial laminate.

- Optimality based PS design shows higher mass energy absorption than LP design
- By help of experimental tests a progressive damage modelling setup was identified

Optimization of variable-axial fiber patterns by using, e.g., DFPO [5]

- Optimizing for maximal mass-specific loads
- Optimizing for even higher energy absorption

Comparison PS1+PS2 vs. PS1 only pattern specimen

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